

Education and Women Empowerment is A Weapon for Sustainable Development of Gender Equality.

Dr. Vaishali Chandrashekhar Yeske

Assistant Professor & IQAC Co-Ordinator, Jaikranti College of Education, Latur

Corresponding Author – Dr. Vaishali Chandrashekhar Yeske

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18516550

Abstract:

Women's empowerment and gender equality mean ensuring women and girls have the same rights, resources, opportunities, and power as men, allowing them to reach their full potential, make their own choices, participate equality in society, which drives broader social, economic, and sustainable development by addressing historical disadvantages and power imbalance for a fairer world.

Women empowerment may be defined in several ways, including accepting women's viewpoints, making an effort to seek them and raising the status of women through education, awareness, and literacy, equal status in society, better livelihood and training. Women's empowerment equips and allows women to make life-determining decisions through the different societal problems. They may have the opportunity to redefine gender roles or other such roles, which allow them more freedom to pursue desired goals.

"No need to hurry, No need to sparkle, no need to be anybody but oneself" Virginia Woolf

Keywords: Sustainable, Empowerment, Weapon, Inequality, Disadvantages, Life-determining etc.,

Introduction:

"There is no chance for the welfare of the world unless the condition of women is improved. It is not possible for a bird to fly on one wing."

Swami Vivekananda

Gender Equality:

UNICEF defines gender quality as ensuring girls and boys, women and men, enjoy the same rights, resources, Opportunities, and protections free from violence and discrimination, acknowledging that different needs require fair, not always identical, treatment to achieve equal outcomes. It means valuing everyone's needs and aspirations equally and removing limitations set by gender stereotypes for sustainable development.

Women empowerment and gender equality are essential for achieving social justice, economic development, and human rights. Despite progress, women continue to face discrimination, inequality, and violence,

hindering their participation in social, economic, and political spheres. In today's world, gender inequality is closely linked to women's rights. All over the world, women and underage girls are subjected to many harmful activities, including sex trafficking. To eliminate this, education and women empowerment will help.

Gender equity is the process of being fair to women and men. To ensure fairness, strategies and measures must often be available to compensate for women's historical and social disadvantages that prevent women and men from otherwise operating on a level playing field. Equity leads to equality. Gender equality requires equal enjoyment by women and men of socially-valued goods, opportunities, resources and rewards. Where gender inequality exists, it is generally women who are excluded or disadvantaged in relation to decision-making and access to economic and social resources.

An overview on women education, empowerment and gender equality:

Achieving gender equality and empowering all women and girls is not just right thing to do, it's essential for sustainable development. Gender equality is not only a fundamental human right, but a necessary foundation for a peaceful, prosperous and sustainable world. There has been progress over the last decades, but the world is not on track to achieve gender equality by 2030.

Women and girls represent half of the world's population and therefore also half of potential. But gender inequality persists everywhere and hurdles for social progress. Sexual violence and exploitation, the unequal division of unpaid care and domestic work, and discrimination in public office, all remain huge barriers. On average, women in the labor market still occupy only 30 percent of managerial positions globally and women spend about two and a half times as many hours in unpaid domestic and care work as men.

At the rate of progress as of 2023, it would take an estimated 300 years to end child marriage, 286 years to close gaps in legal protection and remove discriminatory laws, 140 years for women to be represented equally in position of power and leadership in the workplace, and 47 years to achieve equal representation in national parliaments.

Political leadership, investments and comprehensive policy reforms are needed to dismantle systemic barriers to achieving gender equality is a cross-cutting objective and must be a key focus of national policies, budgets and institutions.

Review of Literature:

Devi, (2017) highlight to the existence of a few key determinants of inequalities prevailing in our country to understand the extent of women empowerment. He also throws light on gender

equality and women empowerment in education, economic participation, resources and political fields. Substantial progress towards gender parity in primary, secondary as well as higher education is achieved slowly. Feminization of workplace, mobility and participation of women in decision making, social and political grounds are noticed but pitiable. Higher education, gender sensitive education system, employment, political participation, elimination of child marriage, training programme etc are recommended for gender equality and women empowerment.

Panda, (2017) highlights the unequal status of women with men and the necessity of women empowerment in the areas of decision making, education, employment etc. He also analyses the influential factors such as gender discrimination, responsibility of family, risk bearing ability and so on. Illiteracy, poverty, health & safety, professional skill, family burden etc are the constraints which stand in the way of women empowerment in India. He further comments that the government policy alone cannot make the women empowerment possible, the cooperation of the society, change in mindset of men etc are essential.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the necessity of women empowerment.
2. To identify the barriers of women empowerment.
3. To suggest some measures for smooth implementation of women empowerment in India.
4. To know various causes of gender inequality.
5. To know how we can eliminate gender inequality.
6. To know gender equality ensures women empowerment.

Methodology:

The present paper is a descriptive analysis of women empowerment and gender equality as a global issue, for which researcher have taken data from secondary source that are research articles, books, periodicals records and government publications.

Need for Women Empowerment:

Need for women empowerment is endless, boundless in India. Following are some of these needs to empower the women.

- To abolish the impact of gender discrimination, inequality and injustice.
- To provide them safety and security in daily life.
- To ensure a fear free workplace for women.
- To make them strong to combat against exploitation.
- To avail legal protection against domestic violence and corruption.
- To make them eligible and effective to contribute to the society.
- To make them able to stand on their own feet.

Schemes for Women Empowerment:

A number of schemes for women empowerment are in exercise in India. Few of which are mentioned below [(Prathiba, 2017), (Panda, 2017), (Shettar, 2015), (www.wbkanyashree.gov.in)].

- Beti Bachao Beti Padhao Scheme
- SWADHAR Greh (A Scheme for Women in Difficult Circumstances)
- Mahila Samridhi Yojana (MSY) October, 1993
- Indira Mahila Yojana (IMY) 1995
- Support to Training and Employment Programme for Women (STEP)
- National Mission for Empowerment of Women
- Rajiv Gandhi Scheme for Empowerment of Adolescence Girls (RGSEAG) 2010
- Dhanalakshmi 2008

- Ujjawala 2007
- Women's Development Corporation Scheme (WDCS)
- Working Women's Forum
- Mahila Samiti Yojana
- Indira Priyadarshini Yojana

Conclusion:

“Educate your women first and leave them to themselves: then they will tell you what reforms are necessary for them.” Swami Vivekananda

In India, education is as a weapon but some of the states remained lack of facilities for education, health awareness and social reforms so it is necessary to develop a view among the society and people about education especially for women and girls which will be helpful for the sustainable development of a nation. A great social reformer Mahatma Phule said that, “Who have a cradle rope, will change the nation.” Primary and Higher Secondary Education will built a wide perspective for girl's education. It will be benefitted with confidence, self-realization, self-awareness and esteem.

References:

1. Devi, T. R. (2017). “Gender Equality: Women Empowerment”, GJRA-Global Journal For Research Analysis, Volume 6, Issue 9, Special Issue September, 2017, ISSN No. 2277-8160, pp.141-143.
2. Panda, D. (2017). “Women Empowerment in India: Rationale and Present State”, International Journal of Emerging Research in Management & Technology, Volume. 6, Issue-9, ISSN:2278-9359, pp.169-175.
3. Prathiba, L. (2017). “A Study on Issues and Challenges of Women Empowerment in India”, GJRA-Global Journal for Research Analysis, Volume 6, Issue 9, Special Issue September, 2017, ISSN No. 2277-8160, pp138-140.
4. United Nations: Gender equality and women's empowerment
<https://share.google/xRSk7jshaDPp5zivX>